

POLITICS, POLITICAL PSYCHOLOGY IN THE CONTEXT OF HERESTHETIC ALGORITHMS AND THE DESIGN OF SOCIETY

(The Other Side of the Coin)

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ABSTRACT

Politics has been an intrinsic and essential component of human existence and society from time immemorial, owing to the inherent political nature of human beings. The diverse cognitive processes and psychological inclinations shown by individuals have unveiled several domains of discord. The inherent challenges arising from divergent interests and interpersonal conflicts have served as the fundamental underpinnings of the field of politics. This domain encompasses several aspects of contention, including power dynamics, authoritative control, economic governance, manipulative tactics, falsehoods,

populism, and numerous other algorithmic manipulations. While politics and policy are sometimes used interchangeably, it is important to note that there are distinct distinctions between these two concepts. Politics may be seen as a discipline including the management of information and techniques, as well as the broader idea of societal organization, the establishment of social order, and the art of reaching compromises. Political psychology is an academic and multidisciplinary discipline that investigates the intersection of political science and psychology. Political representation, opposition, and political involvement are essential components within democratic systems. Democracy, in this context, is founded upon the

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fundamental ideals of liberty, egalitarianism, pluralism, and active engagement. The fundamental elements included within its framework are political liberty, adherence to legal principles, division of governmental authority, secular governance, openness, responsibility, and checks on the use of power. Within democratic systems, the constitution ensures the provision of these fundamental prerequisites. In the present investigation, we attempted to elucidate this idea by using the metaphorical concept of the "front side of the coin". In the section pertaining to the alternative perspective, we observe the utilization of political algorithms and manipulation tactics, political engineering strategies, societal implications of political engineering, as well as

the establishment of political institutions, media control, and political marketing. These approaches are advocated with a belief system that deems all actions as acceptable and justifiable in order to maintain authority within flawed democratic systems. Propaganda, perception management, etc. The nature and methodology of the investigations were examined. Furthermore, attempts have been made to disseminate forecasts about the use of diverse algorithmic procedures in conjunction with artificial intelligence technology, so affording politicians with electoral advantages.

Key Words: *Politics, Democracy, Populism, Political Manipulation, Political Algorithms, Artificial Intelligence*

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INTRODUCTION

Individuals came to recognize the essential nature of living in a community as social creatures. Upon this realization, they began contemplating the means and companions with whom they might address their many demands and challenges, actively seeking out viable answers. The individual first assessed their surroundings and then posed the question, "In what ways could this particular circumstance be improved?" The individuals engaged in the development of potential resolutions and articulated their viewpoints.

Throughout history, thinkers have sought to address various issues related to the social order, state structure, exercise of power, its legitimacy, limitations, and control. These concepts remain relevant in contemporary thought systems aimed at generating solutions. Additionally, thinkers have proposed institutions and mechanisms to facilitate these solutions. From an individual perspective, these discussions encompass topics such as the individual's position within society, their rights and powers, as well as concepts of freedom and equality. The evaluation of the themes was attempted within the historical context and in consideration of the prevailing political circumstances. Hence, the need for individuals to reside inside a societal framework has brought to light the emergence of "politics," a phenomena that is predicated around the variances inherent in communal existence. This phenomena encompasses the evaluation of the creation and distribution of societal values within a framework of justice, with a particular focus on the role of authority. However, when the distribution of produced values in a society is not equitable and certain groups and organizations attempt to influence the allocation of resources based on their own interests, this situation can be categorized as a political phenomenon.

The need to foster shared values, address collective challenges, and develop institutions and organizations dedicated to resolving these issues and delivering public services has

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necessitated the formation of a "management organization" inside societies. Organizations of this kind, known as "political systems," are present globally. The efficacy of political systems relies on the presence of lawful authority to maintain its powers. In this scenario, the acceptance of judgments made by the system is contingent upon the members of society. Failure to comply with these decisions may result in the system resorting to the use of force (Dursun, 2018).

II. The United States of America in the Post-World War II Era. The ascendancy of scientific inquiry and the proliferation of both qualitative and quantitative research conducted within academic institutions have played a crucial role in the advancement of the field of Social Science, leading to notable progress in the discipline of Political Science (Gulbenkian Commission, 1995).

The discipline of political science has a long history, tracing back to the Ancient Greek period. Initially, it was seen as a field of study related to the functioning of the state and was analyzed within the domains of law, sociology, history, and economics. However, in the present day, it has evolved significantly and is now in its second century of development in the 20th century. The concept of politics in the United States may be characterized as a contest for power, with this fight being a significant factor. Political science, previously categorized under "political philosophy" until the "behaviorist revolution" in the 1980s, is expanding its scope beyond the state (Çam, 1987). This expansion entails the inclusion of social processes, such as protest movements, community organizations, and activities of pressure groups. According to Dursun (2018), Currently, the primary focus of the field of political science is on the concept of "political power." The primary differentiating factor is to the dynamics of authority, power, and

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power relations (Kapani, 2000). In the present context, the field of political science encompasses the examination of political views, values, and ideologies. Its objective is to generate intellectual understanding by the application of rationality and adherence to established standards, while also considering empirical and experimental approaches.

Through his academic pursuits, he seeks to cultivate a cognitive mindset that is characterized by critical inquiry, analytical thinking, and the ability to engage in rational discourse. This endeavor involves the pursuit of epistemic justification, the evaluation of cognitive achievements, and the promotion of hypotechnical and algorithmic thinking. In the 21st century, the composition of societies that will shape the trajectory of progress and advancement will be limited to persons who possess the capacity for critical inquiry. These people will possess the ability to analyze events with a higher degree of criticality, creativity, and objectivity, hence promoting the prevalence of scientific thinking in a broader sense. According to the study conducted by Demir and Akınoğlu in 2010, it was found that...

Political science derives additional advantages from interdisciplinary collaboration with other areas of research. This is achieved by the systematic collection of political observations, subsequent analysis of the gathered data, and the rigorous testing of resulting conclusions using empirical evidence. Political science draws upon a range of disciplines, including sociology, economics, public administration, history, geography and geopolitics, law, theology, and psychology. However, it faces inherent challenges such as the heterogeneous nature of society, the presence of multiple variables in analysis, the inability to explain relationships in isolation, and the diverse perceptual frameworks underlying political events. The significance in political reality is in the realm of human conduct. The primary objective of psychological science is to comprehensively comprehend the intricacies of mental processes and human behavior, while using rigorous

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scientific methodologies to elucidate and explicate these phenomena. According to Mc Graw-Hill (2015), the concept in question comprises not only human actions, but also the biological processes that sustain cognitive functions, emotional experiences, perceptual abilities, reasoning capabilities, memory functions, and physiological activities. Consequently, it attempts to elucidate the underlying factors that drive individuals' behavior in relation to any given matter. In brief, political psychology, a subfield within the discipline of psychology, investigates the interplay between politics and psychology. Political psychology examines the interconnections between political events and society, therefore elucidating a comprehensive framework for understanding these phenomena. This cluster encompasses several activities such as leadership and followership, mass psychology, migration and immigration, integration, social traumas, the persuasion of public opinion, winning elections, and voting behavior. Political psychology is an academic discipline and research topic that examines the interplay between psychological elements and human political behavior, attitudes, and decision-making processes (Arıboğan, 2020).

In this context, a prevalent subject of interest within the realms of politics and political psychology pertains to societal matters such as political tensions, disputes, divergent perspectives, societal shifts, economic challenges, and uncertainties arising from inequities in production and distribution. It is imperative to acknowledge the significance of understanding the challenges that emerge in the interplay between policies and individuals within the realm of politics. Politicians employ algorithmic planning to address these issues, while also considering the prioritization of various factors. Furthermore, they utilize heresthetic and rhetorical techniques within this context to attain desired outcomes. Additionally, it is crucial to examine the political manipulations

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observed in pathological democracies. Within the framework of this particular situation, the present paper aims to explore the underlying motivations behind the political science discipline's desire to draw from the field of psychology for its own advantage. What is the significance of the correlation between politics and psychology? To what extent do political actions and attitudes influence political events? What are the goals for which politicians use political psychology? What are the algorithms used in political contexts within pathological democracies? Artificial Intelligence (AI) is used in the realm of politics for many purposes. This technology is utilized to enhance decision-making processes, optimize resource allocation, and improve the efficiency of political systems. The application of AI in politics involves the utilization of algorithms and machine learning techniques to analyze vast amounts of data, identify patterns, and provide insights that aid in formulating informed policies and strategies. By using AI, political actors may get a deeper understanding of public sentiment, predict electoral outcomes, and tailor Efforts will be made to get answers to the inquiries you have posed.

AIM

The term "politics" encompasses the activities involved in managing a society, including the regulation and management of both internal and foreign affairs of the state. It also encompasses the many perspectives and opinions held on this topic, as well as the numerous techniques and concepts used in the practice of politics. The term, originating from the Sumerian language, has its Western counterpart in the Greek term "politics". The term "politics" encompasses several aspects derived from the Greek word "pōise," which pertains to the city-state. It encompasses concepts related to political organization, the rights of citizens, political systems, and republican forms of government (Küçükalp,

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2012). Acknowledging the inherent connection between politics and individuals within a community, it becomes apparent that complete detachment from political influences is unattainable due to the diversity of views and psychological inclinations among individuals. Consequently, this dynamic engenders a state of intrigue and discord, serving as the foundation upon which politics is constructed. Furthermore, politics encompasses a multitude of characteristics, as elucidated by Heywood (2013), including the use of power, the exercise of authority, the process of collective decision-making, the management of limited resources, and the practice of deceit and manipulation.

Political science first emerged throughout the 16th century. The discourse extends till the conclusion of Jean Bodin's work. Subsequently, Jeremy Bentham expanded the scope of this notion, originally confined to the state, by seeing it as an endeavor that extends beyond the state. The Germans, in turn, referred to this expanded idea as "political science" (Türk, 2011). Political science is a field within the social sciences that focuses on the analysis of political ideas, ideologies, and societal values. It encompasses the study of political events and empirical data. The objective of this study is to elucidate the significance of political facts, actions, events, and organizations within the given social structure. Additionally, it aims to categorize them by establishing their interrelationships (Dursun, 2012).

The topic of political psychology has emerged as a significant area of study within both politics and psychology, providing a means to explore the underlying motivations and influences behind political choices and acts (Özer, 2014). Political psychology has a distinct position due to its recognition of the interdependent nature of human personality and politics. According to Eker (2012), the assertion posits that there exists a reciprocal relationship between personality and political conduct, wherein the former influences the latter, and conversely, political events and circumstances impact an individual's

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personality. Political psychology is an interdisciplinary discipline that seeks to explain several phenomena, including voting behavior, mass actions, terrorism, racism, internal and international policy, and the psychology of leaders. Within this particular setting, political psychology operates on the premise that psychological elements play a significant role in shaping an individual's political orientation.

This article examines the tools employed to manipulate political behavior, specifically within the realm of political psychology. It focuses on their application in pathological democracies and explores the algorithmic solutions utilized to analyze both rational and irrational behaviors stemming from the political attitudes and emotions of individuals and groups. The discussion is framed within the context of technological advancements that underpin the development of 21st-century skills. The present study aimed to investigate and elucidate the potential applications of "artificial intelligence" and assess its feasibility.

METHOD

Research: The present work, entitled "Heresthetic Algorithms of Politics and Design of Society in the Context of Political Psychology," is a unique review piece that has been meticulously crafted via an extensive examination of both local and foreign literature sources.

FINDINGS

a) The current study, titled "Heresthetic Algorithms of Politics and Design of Society in the Context of Political Psychology," is a distinctive literature evaluation that

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has been carefully developed via a comprehensive analysis of domestic and international scholarly sources

Obverse of the Coin

Politics and Democracy as Indispensable Elements of Human and Social Life

- a. Human beings are creatures with a rational existence throughout the universe. Being biosocial, it is a social entity that exemplifies the highest development of all living organisms, social life forms, labor, communication and consciousness in the world. It is a being that asks, questions, thinks, has values, beliefs, emotions, priorities and spirituality, and can also use its will.
- b. in the universe , but has a heart that does not fit into the universe. In this context, human beings are both biological and psychological beings, therefore they have a biopsychic integrity. As a transcendent being, it is called "a small world" with the analogy that it is a reflection of the universe. However, at this point where technology has reached today, human emotions, thoughts and perceptions have become received and managed through "smart technologies" created by people with their own hands and minds. (Değirmenci, 2022). In the age of algorithms we live in, our minds and emotions are guided by the dominant algorithmic thinking, and with our own consent. In our era, where artificial intelligence has also come into play, there is a "zeitgeist", an absolute spirit, which, in Hegel's words, expresses the dominant spirit of the period we live in. This spirit today affects societies and states as well as the individual. It's like the

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feelings, thoughts and perceptions of the past; It remains like a "core within the shell of the present", which, in Foucault's view, creates a "biopower" and a "panopticon".

- c. Although society is simply understood as the unity of people who came together in ancient times to meet their common needs, it is academically defined as "the interaction of many people living in a certain geographical location and sharing a common culture to meet their social needs." From a philosophical perspective, society is much more than the numerical sum of individuals. Society, the most basic concept of sociology, is the relationships between people who share a certain culture and certain social rules, the values and behavioral patterns they share. These are systems of relationships that change and develop. According to Emile Durkheim, who is known as the founder of French sociology, the basis of social reality is; is social consciousness. Social consciousness; It is defined as "the combination of the forms of perception, thinking and behavior that consciousness, defined as the moral compass acquired by individuals, embodies in institutional organizations due to the additions people make throughout their lives in accordance with the spirit of the time (Taş MR 2019). Social consciousness is an ongoing process independent of individual consciousness. Groups are formed in society when people with similar characteristics come together, and conflicts may arise due to different views between the groups. Politics is also an area of conflict experienced by individuals and groups in society, because politics is one of the basic social institutions, and politics can also be defined as a struggle for power. In this sense, contradictions between social groups that arise due to wanting to prevent each other from realizing their goals and

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interests or because their ideas are incompatible cause conflicts. Minimizing conflicts and frictions is possible with social integration , therefore social development can be achieved because society has the capacity to tolerate conflicts (Yıldırım, 2019).

- d. Achieving social order took place over a long historical process. Montesquie: “While people lived their primitive lives, they were governed by the laws of nature, and there were no conflicts of interest. " With the transition to social order, they began to lose the equality and freedom provided by the laws of nature" (Montesquie, 1963). Rousseau says; He argues that people living in society can be ensured to be free and equal, as they were at that time, through social contracts. He says that in the transition to this order, there will be a ruling class and a ruled class, and the important thing is that the balanced distribution of rights and interests between these two classes should be achieved, that is, it should be possible to reconcile what justice approves with what interest requires. Therefore, with this discourse, he both expressed the interdisciplinary nature of political science and revealed the principle of "rule of law", which is the basis of the democratic regime (Rousseau, 1965).
- e. consists of written and unwritten rules, norms and principles that regulate the interaction between the rulers and the governed, and is based on the constitution." Therefore, we can also understand political regime in the narrow sense as constitution and political laws. Political regimes are classified as three different types in political science: Democracies, authoritarian regimes and totalitarian regimes (Kalaycıoğlu, 2017). The main thing in democracies is the government of "the people, by the people, for the people". Indispensable elements of democracies are political

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representation, opposition and political participation (Kalaycıoğlu, 2017). Although Sartori says, "Democracy does not have a single author who is more famous than all of them," similar qualifications are made in terms of the institutions and principles put forward by the thinkers; Democracy is based on the principle of individual freedom, equality, pluralism and participation. In this context, democracy is "not a struggle to obtain and remain in power, but a set of principles, values, methods and institutions that can be both a goal, a guide and a tool in individual and social development at the same time" (Caniklioğlu, 2007).

Nevertheless, according to Beriş (2019), the establishment of democracy does not ensure its consistent and uninterrupted operation, therefore necessitating ongoing efforts to reinforce its foundations. Nevertheless, safeguarding and maintaining democracy poses significant challenges owing to its inherent characteristics... Democracy is considered the governing type that relies on little coercion and maximum consent when compared to other models. According to Canikoğlu (2007), The comprehension of democracy inside a nation necessitates an examination not alone of constitutional assurances, but also of the challenges that emerge in the course of implementing constitutional tenets. According to Caniklioğlu (2007), a country cannot be considered democratic solely based on the presence of a democratic constitution, if its internal peace is compromised, if its political institutions are in conflict with other institutions and its citizens, and if the boundaries between public and private spaces are blurred. According to Kışlalı (1997), democracy, being the system that best upholds human dignity, presents challenges in terms of its protection and maintenance. In the present context, democracy can be seen as a particular system of governance that aims to establish and maintain an improved societal structure.

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It is often believed that democracy functions with the purpose of granting individuals the highest degree of personal liberty while simultaneously maintaining order and security within the state (Özer, 1996).

[Political Socialization, Political Behavior and Political Participation.](#)

Political Socialization: Socialization is the term used to describe the acquisition of societal standards, the development of political culture, value judgments, and the establishment of behavioral regulations within a given society. Hence, political scholars often designate this phenomenon of political consciousness as "political learning". The process of learning unfolds gradually and progressively, first with the establishment of generalizations throughout infancy and thereafter evolving into the formation of perspectives, cognitions, attitudes, and actions via the acquisition of education (Turan, 1976). The factors that contribute to and influence political socialization include primary sources such as family, educational institutions, peer groups, media, personal experiences of witnessing war or terrorist incidents, events that significantly impact the nation, and the demise or killing of a revered leader (Saribay, Ögün, 2013).

Political Behaviors: According to sociological perspectives, politics is a pervasive aspect of social interactions, encompassing the exercise of power within the framework of the state apparatus (Bahar, 2009). Consequently, it is intricately linked to societal processes of control, restriction, and subjugation (Foucault, 2003). Social psychology perspectives believe that human behavior is intricately connected to both environmental circumstances and psychological personality characteristics, hence suggesting that actions emerge as a result of the interplay between individual dispositions and external contextual influences. According to Freud, human conduct is influenced by motives originating from many

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levels within the structure of the psyche, as well as from diverse sources (Dursun, 2018). Political attitudes refer to the inclinations that have an influence on the development of individual action. Attitudes, which include the dimensions of integrity, emotion, thinking, and conduct, represent the individual's responses to environmental stimuli. Within this particular context, political conduct may be seen as a responsive reaction, including attitudes and actions shown by individuals in response to the influences emanating from the political environment around them (Öztekin, 2016).

Changing deeply ingrained stereotypical views may be a challenging endeavor, although altering less firmly held attitudes tends to be comparatively more manageable. Nevertheless, alterations in environmental influences, the acquisition of education, the attainment of professional rank, changes in location and domicile, or the achievement of economic success might potentially result in shifts in views. Political involvement refers to the engagement of individuals in political activities, serving as a means of expressing their stance towards the political system via action (Tatar, 1997). These actions pertain to the endeavors undertaken by individuals who are not affiliated with the government, with the intention of exerting influence over the decision-making processes carried out by political authorities. Political participation refers to the dynamic interaction between individuals who are part of a political community and the governing authorities who exercise their power and authority (Dursun, 2018). These acts may be categorized as either autonomous or dependent. According to Kalaycıoğlu, the term "political lobbying" refers to the deliberate efforts and endeavors undertaken by individuals to exert influence on others who are either in or seeking political decision-making positions. This influence is exerted via the choices and decisions made by these individuals, which are done independently and autonomously. Whether the conduct is lawful or illegal does not alter this phenomena of involvement (Kalaycıoğlu, 1998). According to Huntington and

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Nelson, these actions may be classified as "endeavors undertaken by individuals outside of the government with the intention of exerting influence on governmental decision-making processes." Kapani argued that it is insufficient to only focus on voting behavior when examining these activities, since a comprehensive analysis should include a wide range of intensive acts that encompass all political views and activities.

Furthermore, Dahl (1963) classified political involvement into three dimensions: caring, knowledge, and action. Kapani (1998) further conceptualized this classification as a hierarchical structure consisting of three stages: observing events, expressing attitudes and opinions about events, and actively engaging as a subject in these events. Political involvement is a crucial component within a democratic society, giving individuals the ability to actively engage in shaping the societal landscape. Consequently, safeguarding this fundamental right becomes imperative in such a scenario.

Concepts of Public Opinion, Power and Election,

Concept of Public Opinion:

The definition of the term "public" is elucidated in the Dictionary of Sociology Terms, which was published by the Turkish Language Association. According to this source, the public refers to a social group that emerges based on shared interests, forming a community whose members engage in interactions aimed at making decisions pertaining to these shared interests (Hançerlioğlu, 1993). The term "public" is used as a comprehensive term including the notions of "public", "non-private", and "public" (Onaran, 1994). The second component of this conceptual framework, referred to as "vote," is closely associated with the evolution of the notion of the public. It signifies the

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act of expressing one's opinion and thoughts on a contentious matter. However, it is also often interpreted as an act that signifies an individual's deliberate decision-making in relation to any matter within the realm of politics or society (Bektaş, 1996). Neumann's theoretical framework pertaining to public opinion encompasses two distinct perspectives: the first being the notion of public opinion grounded in reason within democratic systems, and the second being the understanding of public opinion as a vehicle for social control. In the context of rationality-based public opinion, effective public opinion necessitates purposeful and conscious communication from the general public to the governing body. This form of public opinion serves a distinct function and is characterized by its intentional nature. Conversely, the socio-psychological perspective of public opinion is viewed as a mechanism of control. It is not deliberate or conscious and operates with an implicit function (Neumann, 1998). The process of preparing the general public for a certain behavior involves the cultivation of a particular coherence in the emotions, ideas, and beliefs held by people or groups in relation to a topic or occurrence that they see as problematic. While it is widely acknowledged that attitudes, particularly those categorized as "pre-tendency," play a significant role in shaping public opinion, it is important to note that attitudes and views are distinct from one another. Attitudes may be characterized as possessing emotive and broad attributes, whilst views can be conceptualized as articulated attitudes, including both ambiguous and precise elements. It is noteworthy that attitudes exhibit a more reasoned framework compared to opinions. The creation of public opinion is influenced by several factors, including the individual's familial, group, educational, occupational, and influential figures within society (Abadan, 1990). Opinion leaders are individuals of prominent stature who command respect from the general public and whose views serve as a foundational reference point. Neumann (1988) proposed the "Spiral of Silence Rule" as a framework for understanding the formation of public opinion. This theory posits that individuals are

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more likely to express their ideas in public if they perceive their viewpoints to align with the prevailing consensus. Conversely, individuals tend to remain silent and exercise caution when they perceive their perspectives to be in the minority, and this pattern persists until their viewpoints become socially stigmatized. According to Duhm (1996), one prevalent defensive mechanism used to counter this anxiety and shape public opinion is the act of adapting and submitting. In summary, those who align themselves with the prevailing ideology tend to possess a more prominent platform for expression and may even exhibit assertive behavior, while others who do not align themselves with this ideology are compelled to maintain a state of silence. In this particular scenario, the government endeavors to use the "media" as a means to instill the concept of consensus public opinion into the collective awareness of society, so validating and fortifying its political agenda (Bourdieu, 1995). The first stage in shaping public opinion involves the unrestricted expression of ideas, the capacity to convey alternative viewpoints without limitations, and the unhindered observation and interpretation of disseminated information and concepts (Bektaş, 1996). The concept of political power refers to the ability of individuals or groups to exert influence and control over the decision-making processes and actions inside a political system. It encompasses the capacity to shape policies, allocate resources, and In the previous discussion on the concept of general politics, it was posited that it might be characterized as a contest for power. In this context, the specific kind of power under consideration is political power. The term "political power" refers to the comprehensive authority that encompasses a whole nation and its societal structures. In this context, the government has authority, control, and the ability to impose penalties on all individuals and collectives residing inside the territorial boundaries of the nation. The term may be defined as follows. According to Öztekin (2016), political power is a kind of authority that encompasses the whole of society inside a nation-state, exerting influence on individuals and shaping their actions. According to

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Dursun (2018), power is a phenomenon that arises via a reciprocal process and mostly manifests itself through interactions. This contact takes place between the governing authority and the governed population.

The government entity responsible for providing this service. The fundamental attributes of a nation-state include the comprehensive inclusion of society within its territorial confines, the absence of a superior authority, the exclusive control over the use of physical force and coercion, and the foundation of its legitimacy on the principles of consent and obedience. The concept of "the authority of political power" refers to the phenomenon whereby legitimate power is able to assert its statements and commands without resorting to force or coercion, and society complies without engaging in critical examination or debate on their validity (Daver, 1993). Nevertheless, when a dominant political authority, possessing exclusive control over the use of force, acquires legitimacy and authority through rational laws that are universally binding, it adheres to predetermined norms and abides by rational and legal regulations during the acquisition, implementation, and preservation of its power. According to Eryılmaz (2002), the legitimacy of a government is contingent upon its ability to secure the agreement of the governed. Political power may be seen as the force behind these interactions that establish the "authority-based allocation of values" inside a given society (Lapierre, 1973). Furthermore, it is intricately connected to the legislative, executive, and judicial functions, forming a cohesive entity. The exercise of power is regulated by a system of checks and balances, and its scope is constrained by constitutional provisions, regulations, and established practices (Kapani, 2004).

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Concept of Election:

The Turkish Language Association provides a definition of election as the process of selecting one or more candidates from a pool of candidates, in line with established rules and regulations. The granting of rights to individuals and the decision-making process in democratic societies are closely intertwined, since the legitimacy of political authority is derived from the "people's will" that is concretely shown via elections. Hence, elections serve as a fundamental indicator of the democratic nature of political institutions inside nations. Furthermore, elections play a crucial role in facilitating the legitimate and effective exercise of national sovereignty. The condition in question is not only adequate for the establishment of democracy, but rather it is deemed indispensable, obligatory, and of fundamental importance. In the context of representative democracies, the formation of assemblies and governments is facilitated by the electoral process (Beetham, 2014). This is due to the fundamental principle of democratic governance, wherein the authority is vested in the people, who exercise their power by electing representatives (Çam, 1990). Standards exist to safeguard the democratic nature of elections, a crucial factor in maintaining the legitimacy of the government. Two key factors that contribute to the integrity of elections are the absence of violence and compulsion, which allows voters to freely express their preferences at the ballot box, and the prevention of manipulations driven by political bias and ideological objectives (Karamustafaoğlu, 1970). The adherence to democratic principles in elections is imperative on a global scale. These principles encompass universal suffrage, equal suffrage, the freedom to vote and participate in elections, the utilization of a secret ballot with open counting and classification, the individual vote principle, the personal vote principle, the direct vote principle, and the principle of judicial resolution in election-related disputes (Derdiman, 2011). Elections serve as a fundamental institution that

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facilitates decision-making processes, making them a paramount component of representative democracy and an essential element within the realm of political affairs. The primary inquiries of significance are to the persons who will assume political leadership roles and thereby determine political outcomes, as well as the circumstances under which these individuals will exercise their decision-making authority.

In Political Decision Making :

In contemporary society, the development of a political and social framework necessitates the prioritization of individuals as its focal point. In contemporary times, the prevailing concept of "divine order" that formerly held sway from antiquity to the present day has been supplanted by an emphasis on social and legal frameworks. Throughout history, political thinkers ranging from Plato to contemporary philosophers have consistently considered the formation and psychological attributes of human beings in their discussions on politics (Çetin, 2003). However, recent advancements in the past century have instigated a transformative process in which politics, influenced by environmental factors, has shaped individuals to align with their surroundings. Insights have emerged regarding the phenomenon of "Character Corrosion," as described by Sennett, which elucidates the process through which individuals undergo redesign. Additionally, Sennett highlights the development and sustenance of the object-subject relationship within a political framework that seeks to impose its objectives. This imposition occurs when political forces intersect with the realities that govern human existence, thereby giving rise to novel dynamics. The concept of "biopower," which is a kind of power, was introduced by Lemke (2017). According to Han (2019), Sennett's characters exemplify the transformation of the person into a self-directed endeavor that

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undergoes continuous restructuring and self-reinvention under the influence of neoliberal policies. Foucault's assertion on the realization of the "end of invented man" is shown by the aforementioned phenomenon (Foucault, 2001). This particular scenario will include the domains of political psychology and the use of infinite heresthetic algorithms by governments.

What is Political Psychology? What are its relevant fields?

"The vast majority of our current or ancient problems, which we consider political, are psychologically based."

D.U. Aribogʻan

Political psychology, although not a recent discovery, is an interdisciplinary area of study that encompasses academic and scientific perspectives. However, its practical application remains limited in many nations and globally. The terminology associated with political psychology has emerged within the scholarly literature during the last century. The idea of "human behavior" has significant importance in the subject of politics, akin to its relevance in psychology. Consequently, it has led to the convergence of Political Science and Psychological Science, resulting in the emergence of a new discipline. Political psychology is an academic field that investigates the cognitive, affective, and behavioral aspects of people, as well as the collective attitudes that shape the identities of larger social groups. Additionally, it explores the underlying causes and manifestations of challenges that arise within the context of political systems. Please refer to the website of Uskudar University for further information about the PPM.politik program. This study investigates the correlation between political choices, political behavior and attitudes, and psychological aspects. It assesses the connection between political processes and political and social behaviors, with a particular focus on empirical

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and cumulative research. Moreover, political psychology delves into the psychological aspects pertaining to the interactions of extensive groups, masses, and countries, as well as their connections with their respective leaders and the interactions among leaders themselves. Consequently, political psychology encompasses both a domestic and global framework. Political psychology is a field of study that investigates the underlying causes of political conduct. It seeks to elucidate the reasonable and illogical actions stemming from various political emotions and attitudes, using a comprehensive approach that encompasses both individual and collective levels of analysis (Çevik Ersay, 2013). Throughout history, the interconnection between politics and psychology has been elucidated by Aristotle through the correlation between "aletheia," denoting the presence of truth, and "politheia," signifying the governance of the morally upright citizen (Bilgin, 2005). The distinctiveness of Political Psychology lies in its recognition of the reciprocal nature of the association between politics and personality. The subject matter may be considered a discipline (Eker, 2012) because to the diverse range of behaviors that can be analyzed, including those that are political, cultural, economic, ideological, emotional, religious, and so on. According to Özer (2014), this phenomenon has many manifestations. Political psychology is a field of study that examines the psychological processes and factors that influence political behavior and attitudes. It seeks to understand how individuals' psychological characteristics, such as personality traits, emotions, and cognitive processes, interact with political contexts to shape political decision-making and participation. This interdisciplinary field draws on theories and methods from psychology, political science, and sociology to investigate topics like The phenomenon in question originated inside the United States during the interwar period. The connection between politics and psychology has been required due to several developments, including the profound impacts of war, the emergence of totalitarian regimes, the prevalence of terrorism, and economic crises (Kurtbaş, 2013). The field of political

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psychology encompasses various domains of inquiry, including but not limited to social reflexes, perceptions, prejudices, voter and elected relations, conflict, violence, terrorism, neopolitical issues, genocide, immigration, and immigrant integration (Ersay, 2013). Additionally, political psychology investigates the processes of socialization and the manifestation of authoritarian tendencies in children, as well as the influences of school, friends, and group dynamics on individuals (Ersay, 2013). (Bilgin, 2005) The issues under consideration include etc. In summary, political psychology is concerned with the correlation between political and spiritual phenomena (Türkçapar and Göka, 1995). Political actors increasingly employ reactive understandings and practices reminiscent of Roman arenas, particularly as election calendars become more condensed. These actors utilize a range of techniques and communication strategies to engage with voters and secure their support. Political psychology, as a field of study, investigates various aspects such as voter behavior, leader behavior, group dynamics, and mass psychology, which are of interest to political actors seeking to effectively reach and mobilize voters (İnan, 2009). Nevertheless, it is crucial to keep a balance between ethical principles and objectivity in the field of political psychology, which encompasses a broad and speculative domain, under the idea that chaos is an inherent aspect of existence, just as much as order (Kurtbaş, 2013).

[The Other Side of the Coin](#)

[Heresthetic Algorithms of Governments and Their Efforts to Design Society](#)

The primary objective of attaining political power is to effectively engage with the electorate's emotions and establish a connection that resonates with them. This connection is crucial in order to secure the support of voters, who function as the

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customers inside the political arena. In democratic nations, political parties engage in efforts to secure voter support via democratic means with the aim of attaining political power. Within democratic institutions, the provision of legal and ethical backing engenders voter support, ultimately translating into a tangible manifestation known as a "vote". Political parties and their candidates use several strategies to garner public support, including the utilization of political communication and political marketing algorithms. Political communication refers to the intricate process of communication that occurs within the triangular framework of political parties, their candidates, and the electorate. Political marketing is a crucial component within this process, since it operates within the confines of this triangular framework. According to Bongrand (1981), political marketing is a significant political communication instrument that becomes more necessary in the context of the proliferation of democracy and the shift towards an information society. Through the use of political marketing techniques, many notable outcomes may be seen. Firstly, the public becomes more educated, leading to greater levels of engagement. Additionally, the emphasis placed on disclosing the country's boundaries serves to concentrate the attention of the people. Moreover, politicians get access to a wealth of technical and comprehensive information, enabling them to more effectively convince voters. According to Tan (2002), voters are the target audience in the realm of political marketing. Political marketing is a domain that need the careful management of a competent and cohesive team, since it is prone to potential political mishaps. In this context, it is crucial to possess a comprehensive understanding of the social and psychological attributes of the intended audience in order to achieve favorable outcomes. In particular, it is essential to acknowledge the significant influence of the media on voter behavior. The contemporary mass media channels that have shown the highest efficacy include television, newspapers, radio, the Internet, media posters, ads, pamphlets, and rallies. In contemporary society, the internet, often referred to as "new

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media," serves as a prominent mass communication medium that amalgamates many forms of visual, audio, and written media. In addition to the well-intentioned research conducted in established democracies globally, it is observed that various Machiavellian algorithms are proposed inside dysfunctional democratic systems. Particularly focusing on the 19th century. The Narodnik movement in Russia originated during the latter half of the year, while the wave of populism observed in Western Europe since the 1990s can be attributed to the 1929 Economic Depression in Latin America. Presently, global concerns such as economic challenges, immigration issues, and the emergence of "authoritarian leadership" in democratic systems have further contributed to the prevalence of populism. The phenomenon under discussion has been identified as a kind of argumentation, a strategic approach, and an algorithmic political style that has seen a resurgence in response to a particular issue, hence fostering the development of novel policy initiatives.

“Populism” as a political algorithm and manipulation strategy

De la Torre's conceptualization of populism may be characterized as a political approach that seeks to attain political power and rule by using a Manichean rhetoric that dichotomizes society into two contrasting factions: the populace and the oligarchy (Ponizza, 2005). The primary focus of this strategic generalization, which now dominates political discourse, is rooted on the observation that populist parties tend to either have the majority in parliament or rank among the biggest political parties after elections. Based on these findings, it may be argued that an excessive number of ideological groups in representative democracies is no longer necessary, as it is more advantageous to use the potential of populism. The phenomenon of populism as conceptualized by Mudde.

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The user's text is already academic in nature. No rewriting is necessary. through the establishment of a dichotomy between the "corrupt elites" and the "virtuous masses." This ideological framework seeks to create a sense of unity and solidarity among the populace, while simultaneously positioning the elites as the primary source of societal problems. Populism asserts that political decision-making should be guided by the collective desires and interests of the people, emphasizing the importance of the general will. Consequently, populism often manifests itself through various means of popular expression. The concept of "us/other" and "people/elite" is often presented as a contrasting framework and is frequently used as symbolic rhetoric within the context of populism (Mudde, 2004). According to Mudde, populism is characterized by the use of emotive speech to stir up popular sentiment, and politicians employ this strategy as a means to secure electoral support using demagogic tactics. According to Mudde (2004), the author posits that populism might be characterized as a kind of "opportunism." Populism is a malleable ideology that is built in a fictitious manner. Specifically, this concept has the potential to be implemented across many political ideologies, hence impacting the level of democratic political engagement. Additionally, it has the capacity to foster the emergence of a new capitalist elite or alternatively, eradicate existing socioeconomic divisions. Furthermore, it has the ability to simultaneously serve as a safeguard against racial discrimination while also engaging in efforts to oppose it. The aforementioned dynamics occur inside the individual occupying the position of leadership, so indicating that populists do not serve as representatives of the populace, but rather as self-interested actors striving to attain political authority (Finchelstein, 2019). In representative democracies, political regimes derive their legitimacy from the adoption of populist ideology or the use of populist language. According to Finchelstein (2019), their objective is to gradually undermine the values and principles of representative democracy, rather than completely dismantle them. They employ a strategy of appearing to uphold the separation of powers while

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simultaneously seeking to consolidate power. Their intention is not to eradicate political opposition, but rather to consistently challenge its legitimacy. They employ tactics such as labeling opponents as "enemies of the people," marginalizing them, and even engaging in demonization, as noted by Müller (2017). In contemporary discourse, populism is often regarded as a "ideal approach," in addition to the other perspectives and definitions already mentioned. The concepts of people, elite, and national will, which are crucial to the theory of Populism, exhibit variations across different countries due to contextual factors (Mudde, 2007). Consequently, these concepts do not possess distinct, all-encompassing ideological ideas or projects, as they encompass diverse ideologies within both right and left ideological frameworks. Within this particular context, it is important to note that the subject at hand is not only an ideology, but rather a discursive framework and a manifestation of politics (Gidron and Bonikowski, 2013). It represents a political attitude that is characterized by its radical nature and its pursuit of power (Freedon, 2003).

Heresthetic Algorithms

According to Gustave Le Bon (1997), the determination of a nation's destiny is no longer only influenced by the decisions made by rulers, but rather by the collective consciousness and beliefs held by the general population. According to Nietzsche, he also posits that the attainment of power comes at a considerable cost, since it has the tendency to diminish intellectual capacity, as seen by his statement: "Power renders individuals intellectually deficient..." In order to assert dominance over a person, political entities must first disturb their psychological state, impair their perception, divert their attention from objective truth, and ultimately render them intellectually stagnant via the use of many manipulative tactics. The ongoing psychological warfare between the government

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and the general populace aims to transform individuals into compliant entities. The government sometimes incites the populace, occasionally participates in dialogues that foster unity among the populace, occasionally implements policies and initiatives with great impact, and in the process, employs various values, conceptions, and religious principles. Consequently, the government has effectively influenced the collective psychology of the population, so establishing a conducive atmosphere for the purpose of deceiving and manipulating the masses. The populace has been subjected to a state of hypnosis, resulting in a diminished inclination for inquiry, a sentiment that aligns with the government's aversion towards scrutiny. Currently, the field of psychology has seen a significant focus on the dynamics of power, particularly in relation to the psychology of the general population. Scholars have observed that the masses might be subject to manipulation in many ways, as highlighted by Anar (2019). The concept of "Art of Heresthetics" refers to the strategies used by governments in pathological democracies with the aim of either retaining or acquiring power. Heresthetics is an artistic practice rooted on the philosophical principles of Machiavellianism (Mclean, 2002). Riker's perspective on heresy might be characterized as embracing the notion of "the art of winning at all costs," aligning with the principles of Machiavellianism. According to this viewpoint, using various manipulative strategies is considered acceptable and appropriate in order to attain one's objectives. According to Machiavelli (1999), heresy may be seen as a strategic approach akin to the "Art of War" when used in the realm of politics. Riker (1986) provided a definition for the term, which originates from the ancient Greek terms "hairesis" and "hairesetikós", denoting preference or choice. According to Riker, it may be understood as "the skillful organization of preferences with the aim of influencing the dynamic manipulation of preference conditions and subsequent outcomes." According to the Roman politician and historian Tacitus, power is the most conspicuous of all human emotions. The desire for power is a consuming passion that profoundly affects the human

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psyche. In his renowned work titled "History of Conspiracies and Counter-Conspiracies," Niccoló Machiavelli, a prominent figure in the field of modern political science, offers guidance to governing bodies on the preservation of power. Machiavelli advocates for the strategic utilization of religion by those in positions of authority, the pragmatic application of force when dealing with the general populace, and the employment of various political manipulations and maneuvers as deemed necessary. Nevertheless, Machiavelli's proposals might be seen as describing a polity characterized by corruption, since he emphasizes that "the people merely observe the outcomes." In the realm of politics, where the objective is to attain or maintain power, the established guidelines are already well-defined. Politics operates on the principle of "interest," with the primary driving force being the pursuit of "interest maximization" (Aktan, 2017). In the present context, heresthetics aligns itself with the Machiavellian doctrine, whereby any methods and strategies to achieve victory are deemed valid and lawful. Consequently, the governing body is not bound by legal, moral, or religious constraints in its pursuit of triumph. The individual in question employs a range of political strategies, including falsehoods, deceit, persuasive language, reciprocal voting arrangements (commonly known as negative log-rolling), fraudulent manipulation of electoral boundaries (referred to as gerrymandering), favoritism towards personal connections in the allocation of government resources (also known as pork-barreling), shaping public opinion through the construction of specific narratives, exerting control over the political agenda, fabricating issues for political gain, and fostering an atmosphere of fear. There are several manipulative tactics, as discussed by Aktan (2022).

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Rhetoric

In his book "Rhetorical Strategy," Riker examines one of the political manipulations wherein he discusses the art of rhetoric as a means of persuasion. He explores how politicians use oratory and appeals to heroism in order to mislead and sway people with the objective of securing their votes. In discussing the philosophy of values, Riker posits that logic is associated with the concept of "correctness" and is primarily concerned with the pursuit of truth. In contrast, the art of rhetoric is characterized as a communicative discipline that seeks to persuade others to embrace one's views, regardless of their inherent validity. Rhetoric is a persuasive communication strategy that aims to convince the audience by using oratory techniques that may obscure or manipulate the facts. Aristotle regarded the "art of rhetoric" as the skill of persuasive oratory in ancient Greece, emphasizing its importance for politicians. However, this concept faced criticism from Plato and Aristophanes, who saw it as an art of deceit and manipulation, primarily used to mislead and manipulate others. In contemporary political discourse, language has emerged as a potent instrument for emotive manipulation, strategically used to shape the collective will of a country.

Political engineering, designing society

The "engineering approach" refers to a design technique in which a problem is first specified, followed by the compilation of relevant information and the conduction of research to find a solution. After the completion of the study, the necessary plans are formulated and then implemented in accordance with the design (Dağ, 2013). The issue of political engineering within the government pertains to the analysis of algorithms that institutions and rules may use to further their objectives, as well as the formulation and

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implementation of corresponding strategies. In this context, the issue is framed as the restructuring of institutions and the establishment of novel regulations to ensure the perpetuation of authority. The primary focus of the government's endeavor is in the creation of political institutions, particularly in relation to the formation of higher judicial bodies, as well as the formulation of the constitution and constitutional regulations (Cooter, 2000). Following this, the discussion will go into the topics of political parties and elections, voting regulations that may potentially benefit the ruling government, as well as the means of engaging in communication with political parties. Engineering tools, such as bargaining, mediation, problem-solving, and negotiation, are employed in political contexts to design and manipulate political systems in order to acquire power, even at the expense of ethical considerations (heraesthetics). Additionally, activities like the reorganization of electoral districts (Aggarwal, 1998) and studies on political communication and the strategic use of media control are utilized for political purposes. The actions found in pathological democracies have been documented by Aktan (2022). Religious and educational institutions, along with other fundamental state institutions, are subject to political engineering by the government due to their potential as conducive contexts for the exercise of influence over individuals' thoughts and beliefs (Aktan, 2022). According to Machiavelli, the state has a significant influence on religion, morality, and law.

Social Engineering

Social engineering may be described as the process of reconstructing societal structures via the use of political mechanisms. Within the field of political science, the term "political influence" is often understood as endeavors aimed at exerting control on

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the actions and conduct of a substantial portion of the populace. The idea is often understood as a framework for the organization of mental processes or the structure of social and psychological awareness. The described phenomenon entails a covert strategic undertaking implemented under the guise of an engineering endeavor, executed by a group endowed with financial backing and using diverse communication tools. Specifically, the aforementioned statement highlights the complex nature of an activity that encompasses a range of initiatives and practices aimed at effecting changes in the demographic composition, social fabric, and historical framework of a given society. The objective of this activity is to exert influence over, regulate, and hinder the societal responses, wishes, and emotions. Movies specifically produced using various media platforms and intended for television viewership inside a certain culture, with the aim of influencing the societal political landscape, programs that glorify violence, and television shows that promote peer victimization within educational institutions are illustrative instances of social engineering. The discipline of "political engineering" encompasses the examination of legal and administrative systems that are intended to shape society. The alteration of societal knowledge repositories, which serve as the fundamental genetic material of a given society, leads to a transformation in the envisioned structure and organization of such society. Political entities seeking to preserve their authority endeavor to mold society according to their desired configuration via the use of mass media. The utilization of manipulation, perception creation, and propaganda techniques is particularly prominent in their approach. In essence, social engineering can be succinctly defined as the process of constructing a novel community that adheres to specific principles (Sağır, 2019). Alternatively, social engineering can be characterized as the manipulation of language, religion, race, culture, and other factors from an alternative standpoint. The process of cultivating and harmonizing the many components that bind a

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community and foster a shared sense of purpose, with the aim of fulfilling political and economic aspirations, may be seen as a kind of "cultural infusion" (Duverger, 1995).

Intelligence ” as a Manipulation Tool

Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to a computer-controlled system that demonstrates human-like behavior, including a wide range of capabilities such as thinking, movement, voice and sound perception. It engages in diverse activities, mirroring the actions of intelligent beings. The objective of artificial intelligence (AI) is to develop computers capable of doing activities that typically need human intellect, so enhancing their cognitive capabilities and ultimately facilitating everyday living. According to Belhadj (2022), There are three significant occurrences in the annals of history. One of the primary aspects under consideration is the genesis of the cosmos. The second marks the beginning of existence. According to Pirim (2006), Edward Fredkin identifies the rise of artificial intelligence as the third factor. The utilization of "expert systems," a fundamental technology within the field of artificial intelligence as highlighted by Fredki, serves as a testament to the remarkable advancements in technology witnessed in the current era. Equipped with the necessary linguistic capabilities, these systems possess the ability to provide commentary, resolve issues, acquire knowledge, impart knowledge, comprehend language, and undertake actions based on linguistic input. He has the ability to engage in the activities of reading, perceiving, and concentrating on textual materials. According to Özmerkez (2020), it is said that...The approach known as "discretion detection" used by data scientists enables the identification of individuals by considering data points that lie outside the inherent clusters within the dataset. Consequently, this technology has the capability to possess a

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deeper understanding of individuals than they have of themselves (Say, 2020). Artificial intelligence, as per scientific literature, is formally characterized as an algorithmic or mathematical construct (Ünal, 2001). Artificial intelligence algorithms include the textual possibilities that facilitate the representation of real-world things inside the computer realm. The term "algorithm" refers to the systematic arrangement of actions in a coherent sequence, intended to address a specific issue or accomplish a desired objective. In the present context, artificial intelligence refers to automated systems capable of generating algorithms. According to Koroğlu (2018), human intelligence is capable of generating algorithms. Artificial intelligence (AI) is widely used across several disciplines, including medicine, sociology, psychology, media studies, political science, and anthropology. Notably, the significance of digital and media anthropology has been increasingly recognized, particularly in the context of electoral processes (Kırık & Özkoçak, 2023). In contemporary times, the significance of the connection between artificial intelligence and elections has grown considerably. This is mostly due to the essential role that propaganda plays in political campaigns. Propaganda is a political instrument used to shape and manipulate public sentiment, with the objective of exerting influence on voter perspectives and consolidating the authority of the governing body. Propaganda refers to a purposeful and organized endeavor, known as a psychological operation, that seeks to disseminate ideas via persuasive means, with the intention of altering public attitudes, molding perceptions and cognitive processes, and influencing behavior. According to Alp (2016), the phenomenon being described may be characterized as a methodical framework for disseminating partial, deceptive, and purposeful data. Hence, these efforts might be regarded as manipulative tactics used to alter voter choices (Özer, 2019). In contemporary times, political entities, particularly governments aiming to maintain their authority, engage in preparatory measures such as voter outreach, preference analysis, and tailored messaging through the utilization of artificial intelligence, big data analysis,

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and algorithms. However, concerns arise regarding the transparency and fairness of elections due to the manipulative nature of these studies. In conclusion, based on the findings of this study, some recommendations might be made. As a social entity, humans, through the advancement of their cognitive capacities, have come to recognize that in order to address the challenges they face, it is essential to reside within a communal framework. Consequently, generating collective resolutions proves to be more advantageous and cost-effective. The disparities in social interactions, the varied approaches to problem-solving, the existence of opposing viewpoints, the intricacies of the political sphere, and the proposed solutions to societal issues have necessitated the establishment of governance structures, giving rise to political systems. The disciplines that were formerly categorized under the field of "political philosophy" are now recognized and classified within the discipline of "political science". Specifically, what should the structure of the social order entail? The emergence of the political and legal entity known as the state is a subject of inquiry. Is there a need for the existence of the state? What is the origin or basis of political power? What ought to be the underlying objective of power? Is the legitimacy of every authority universally recognized? What should be the ideal nature of societal interactions, particularly in terms of the relationship between individuals and power dynamics? In which political systems are freedom and equality considered essential? Are there some aspects that are considered indispensable? Currently, scientific methodologies are used to uncover solutions to these aforementioned issues. Human beings possess both biological and psychological attributes, enabling them to engage in cognitive processes, experience emotions, hold values and ideas, and maintain biopsychic integrity. Consequently, the field of "political psychology" has evolved to include the examination of all political actions within this framework. In the subsequent section of our article, we address inquiries pertaining to the ideal approach to political processes, the application of ethical principles in politics, the operation of

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democracy on various scales, the equitable assurance of equality, freedom, and the rule of law, as well as the determination of what constitutes moral correctness. This section is colloquially referred to as the "front side of the coin." The Manichaeian discourse posits that governments, driven by their passions, deem all forms of manipulation as permissible and legitimate in their pursuit of victory at any cost. Consequently, they employ various strategies such as "pure/public" populism, manipulative methods, herestics, rhetoric, and political engineering to maintain their hold on power. This inquiry explores the manner in which algorithmic activities, political marketing, and unethical communication practices are used within propaganda to shape society and establish new social constructs and cognitive frameworks. The examination of how corrupt governments use "artificial intelligence and complex algorithms," the most recent technological advancements, particularly in electoral processes, was also explored in the "alternative perspective" segment. The findings of these studies indicate that the global surge in populism and the corresponding manipulative tactics employed are regrettably not advantageous for society. Totalitarian regimes intentionally and knowingly divert the collective will of society, employing a manipulation strategy that fosters polarization through the creation of perceived adversaries. The implementation of the "I did it and that's it" mindset, in conjunction with the act of "creation," has been shown to result in abuses of rights. Furthermore, the research also reveals that mental hypnosis was achieved through the establishment of a dominant sense of "rationalizing irrationality," the promotion of the notion of "preserving the existing state of affairs," the cultivation of "collective political behavior," and the implementation of the persuasive impact of the slogan "join the band." These strategies were employed with the objective of exerting control over the mindset of the general population. The use of artificial intelligence and intricate algorithms, particularly in the context of elections, has led to a perception of unfairness and inequity within the collective awareness of the people. What actions should be taken

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in this situation? In what manner and via what means may the drawbacks associated with these disclosed facts be transformed into benefits? Can the use of a quantum methodology enable the transformation of chaos into opportunity? Alternatively, one can argue, drawing inspiration from Dostoyevsky, that the end justifies the means, as shown by the statement "If it's mean, it's mean, as long as you reach your goal." Conversely, another perspective influenced by Dostoyevsky suggests that each individual bears the responsibility for all actions, prior to considering the actions of others, as encapsulated in the assertion "Every person is responsible for everything, before everyone else." In well-established, non-distorted democratic systems, individuals who assume accountability effectively express their desires and preferences via electoral processes. Conversely, in dysfunctional democracies, this fundamental principle is compromised by a range of manipulative tactics and methods. Within this particular framework, politics may be seen as an intangible notion, while those who corrupt this idea are the governing authorities that have influence over the trajectories of societies. Are humans devoid of agency and unable to effect change in their circumstances? The user declines to provide further information. What course of action should be undertaken? It is imperative to avoid being apathetic towards issues such as hunger, poverty, income inequality, disregard for the rule of law, dysfunctional democracies, curtailment of fundamental rights and freedoms, and global economic crises. Instead, it is crucial to approach these events and phenomena with a sense of social responsibility, placing the provision of benefits for humanity above personal interests. The dissemination of awareness, encompassing cognitive processes such as mindfulness, problem recognition, intentionality, and cognition, is imperative at both national and global scales. It is crucial to align political decision-making with the promotion of awareness regarding shared challenges, integrating principles from political psychology. This approach can expedite the constructive transformation of political

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attitudes and behaviors. In conclusion, it is said that the social system exhibits dynamism and perpetuates its existence via processes of renewal.

Restriction

The research is limited to scientific research that has been previously conducted around the world and reported in the literature.

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